

Sydney Startup Hub's Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
General Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 Ecosystem Definition & Evolution	5
1.1 Sydney Startup Hub	5
1.2 Ecosystem Evolution	5
Government Links	7
Council Links	7
Environment Links	7
Incubators Links	7
Media Links	7
Network Links	7
Financial Links	7
Investment NSW	8
Investors	8
2 Leverage Proposal	9
2.1 Vision (Why & What)	9
2.2 Details (Who, How & When)	9
2.3 Incentives (Why)	10
References	11

1 Ecosystem Definition & Evolution

1.1 Sydney Startup Hub

Entrepreneurship is a definition that is deemed too volatile to define, defining entrepreneurship promotes the mind flows and the desire for one to take risk and act upon a specific industry. Entrepreneurial ecosystems refer to the space and the network that entrepreneurs endure to undergo their ideas and processes within an ecosystem that promotes similar mindsets. Ecosystem is a broad term used to describe a community or an interconnected structure. While defining the Ecosystem it is essential to understand the significance of businesses with the Sydney Startup Hub (SSH) which make up the ecosystem. Businesses rely on the ecosystem to promote ideas and give startups a helping hand when pursuing the tough entrepreneurial journey.

SSH in its fine form incubates and accelerates a range of industries within the startup ecosystem to promote and sustain their growth guiding them through the process through access to the wide ecosystem. The ecosystem has allowed Startup businesses to have access to funding, investors, venture capitalists and many more. Businesses in the ecosystem will often look to mentors and take guidance from mentors that are successful in certain fields. Through years of research and competition Startups have become more approachable and incentivised by SSH and Investment NSW, as startups have the ability to focus on the current global issues that require fine attention that may possibly be ignored by much bigger corporations.

However, the ecosystem generates the network to make bonds through business and industry. This is what makes the entrepreneurial ecosystem so effective because of the connection and network generated. SSH prides itself on connecting and promoting startups within the ecosystem, because startups create jobs to better the economy and have a wide range of benefits to an ecosystem. The ecosystem flourishes because of the government backing and promoting which allows the SSH to run and not charge expensive rents to startups who simply can't afford the space yet.

1.2 Ecosystem Evolution

In 2017, the NSW government backed the idea of the Sydney Startup Hub, contributing \$35 million to the project. Premier at the time Gladys Berejiklian highlighted the importance of having a centralised hub in NSW for innovative startup businesses to be held, stating “more than 40 per cent of the nation’s start-ups are in NSW already and with the addition of this hub and the White Bay precinct we want to see that figure grow” (Pearce, 2017). Tech Sydney CEO Dean McEvoy followed up by saying “In this fast-moving industry the knowledge of how to successfully build a high growth technology company has a very short shelf life, so the only way you can accelerate the learning of these founders is to put them close to other founders at a similar stage” (Pearce, 2022). In early 2018, the Sydney Startup Hub officially opened, offering over 17,000 sqm of affordable space in the heart of Sydney CBD capable of accommodating around 1,800 people, making it the highest-density communal space in the Southern Hemisphere. The SSH features three incubators within the 12 floors; Fish burners, Stone & Chalk and Tank Stream Labs and also hosts some of Australia’s biggest companies such as Westpac, Optus and Microsoft. Since opening, the start-ups within the three incubators at the SSH have raised over \$740 million and created almost 6,000 jobs helping

Sydney achieved the ranking as the 19th best city for Start-ups in the world. With the mission statement “We connect, grow, educate, create partnerships, and help to build a culture that enables all actors within the NSW innovation ecosystem to prosper” the SSH has been able to achieve exactly what it was set out to do. Since opening in February 2018, more than 835 start-ups and events have been hosted by the SSH, more than 33,000 people have attended events hosted by the SSH, more than 108,938 people have registered to use community workspaces and hot-desks, more than 3289 regional entrepreneurs have used the temporary desks when visiting Sydney and as of June 2021, over 450 start-ups were based out of the SSH.

These staggering numbers truly showcase the development of the SSH ecosystem and how since its opening, the SSH has fostered many entrepreneurs in their journey to creating a successful startup.

Figure 1: Sydney Startup Hub's Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

Government Links

Government links with network stakeholders as the government communicates with communities and businesses to gain feedback and understand what is needed/wanted by local communities. Furthermore, the government links with financial stakeholders as the government communicates with banks and investment companies to help fund projects to benefit the future; an example is the Net Zero initiative and how the government started the project to reduce emissions. The government also connects with councils as governments introduce rules and legislations that councils and their local communities must apply; furthermore, governments and councils work together to ensure sustainability across certain regions.

Council Links

The council has a link with the environment as the council plays a significant role in ensuring that local communities stay environmentally friendly. Councils provide streets and parks are clean from pollution and ensure enough facilities such as bins and recycling stations. Another link is between Lord Mayor Clover Moore and the Sydney Startup hub incubators. Mayor Clover Moore does all the programming and organising for the incubators. Clover Moore believes incubators are the start of the city's future as businesses will be involved in incubators at their starting phase.

Environment Links

Environmental stakeholders play a significant role in the ecosystem of the Sydney Startup hub. The Sydney Startup hub consists of many up-and-coming environmentally friendly businesses that want to help and contribute to ensuring the future includes sustainable energy and reductions in emissions. The new companies within the Sydney Startup hub are introducing new technologies and methods to ensure the city's future through environmentally friendly technologies. Bomen Solar farms have a link with Lord Mayor Clover Moore as she agreed on a deal with many different farms to supply renewable energy for the city of Sydney. Bomen Solar farms were one of the farms she agreed to an agreement with.

Incubators Links

Within the Sydney Startup Hub, there are many startups at each level. However, two incubators that have been the most significant influence on startups are Fishburners and Stone & Chalk. Fishburners have partnered with the NSW government since operating in the SSH. Stone & Chalk also have been associated with the SSH since its opening. The two significant incubators must communicate with Investment NSW with the government offering financial support to bring more startups to the SSH. Councils also work closely with the incubators as Clover Moore sees the opportunity for more people to work within Central Sydney by increasing entrepreneurial culture and networking opportunities.

Media Links

Media has been this generation's most effective form of communication for many years. Two of the most prominent forms of media are social media and press releases. The Sydney Startup Hub have significantly used these two platforms to raise a more extensive influence on entrepreneurs looking to expand their startups. Press releases have articles about SSH that provide information about how the entrepreneurial ecosystem can help startups and put them in the right direction to becoming successful. LinkedIn is the largest social media platform SSH has, assisting future entrepreneurs in communicating with owners of certain startups by providing insights to guide them and their startups.

Network Links

Networking is crucial for the Sydney Startup Hub. Government agencies work extremely hard to ensure that the SSH is funded appropriately to help startups with a minor financial boost. The SSH must network with other businesses that have established their startups as owners and can provide insights on how to be successful. By networking with communities, the SSH can promote its significance to individuals looking to become entrepreneurs. Individuals can communicate with the SSH about starting their ideas which can help them network with individuals already growing in the SSH that could look to become their mentors.

Financial Links

Sydney Startup Hub requires a large sum of financing to ensure that its entrepreneurial ecosystem is able to operate and succeed. Sydney Startup Hub requires financial funding from various sources to ensure they are financially stable and can operate. Financial institutions such as banks are largely utilised by

Sydney Startup Hub to access large sums of cash through loans where which provides Sydney Startup Hub with quick access to large sums of cash where it must be paid back. Sydney Startup Hub utilises these funds to invest in investments that can grow in value over time such as property and can seek to sell these investments as a means to build capital or capitalise on these investments and use it to enhance the operations of Sydney startup hub. With both financial institutions and investments made by the Sydney Startup hub, this allows for Sydney Startup Hub to capitalise on its finance and utilise it to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Investment NSW

CEO Amy Brown and COO Lisa Braid dictate the goals and direction of Investment NSW which impacts and influences the operations and goals of the Sydney Startup Hub. CEO Amy Brown drives the direction and purpose of the long-term goals of Investment NSW and Sydney Startup Hub whilst COO Lisa Braid assists Amy Brown with identifying issues and direction the Investment NSW should take to ensure that Sydney Startup Hub operations are enhanced and successfully assist startups within the hub.

Investors

Investors of the Sydney Start-up Hub include corporate, venture capitalists, competitors and angel investors, and essentially all have an interest in the success and growth of the startups. Investors are able to help and provide assistance to incubators such as Chalk & Stone and Fishburnes in providing resources and guidance to reach their long-term and short-term goals. Corporate investors include Optus Enterprise and Social Enterprise Finance Australia where their roles are driven by building governance practices that will assist incubators and startups to ensure they operate at a high standard and ensure the success of the organisation. Competitors are startups that are competing within and under the Sydney Startup Hub. With this understanding, Sydney Startup Hub will assist both of these competitors to push through and succeed, regardless of their competition. Angel investors provide financial backing and in return seek equity of the startups and businesses, this includes Oli Capitol and Sydney Angels in assisting the flow of the entrepreneurial ecosystem by helping start-ups gain a financial advantage and capital expenditure. The final type of investor is a venture capitalist similar to angel investors where employees seek to fund start-ups and in return seek a large stake of equity, assisting start-ups financially and guiding them to succeed. Overall, corporate, venture capitalist, competitors and angel investors are all investors that have strong interest in the desire for the start-ups within Sydney Start-up Hub to succeed and grow and in return will have a larger return in the long term whilst also influencing the entrepreneurial ecosystem within the Sydney Start-up Hub.

2 Leverage Proposal

2.1 Vision (Why & What)

Vision defines EE to shape the future of the potential ecosystem and where it will be based on future prospects and initiatives. Over the next 10 years we propose Sydney Start up focuses on targeting high schools and students who are not subject to the teachings of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship in past teachings has often been defined as too risky and irresponsible, however through more success and pathways explaining the benefits of entrepreneurship educators have found a necessity in the teachings of entrepreneurship. High school's traditional teachings have often guided students to the typical route of working lifestyle, however entrepreneurship has learned to promote a much more free flowing lifestyle relying on the innovation of your own work and the passion driving from your own idea.

Over the next 10 years if high schools are targeted as the future of the EE, to take action right now possible comparisons must be made to successful ecosystems such as Silicon Valley. Making comparisons allows our group to identify significant differences in their ecosystem to compare the major differences. The ideal ecosystem can be defined as an ecosystem that is flourishing, SSH's EE has the ability to grow with the possible leverage proposals indicated below.

2.2 Details (Who, How & When)

The appealing audience to accelerate the progression and expansion of the Sydney Start-up Hub is local communities. For Sydney Start-up Hub to progress to the next level, the marketing team must advertise its existence as Sydney Start-up Hub. Many people within the city of Sydney are either unaware that the start-up hub exists or do not understand what the start-up has to offer. For this reason, we believe that the start-up hub should market and network itself within local councils and local communities. Many children and adults in local communities do not have the opportunity to access high levels of education such as university.

For this reason, many miss out on the chance of knowing that the start-up exists. Many people within Sydney's local communities have ideas and interests in starting a business; however, they reach a significant obstacle when making this idea a reality and do not know where to start or who to talk to; the start-up hub offers these opportunities. To stop this and spread the awareness of SSH in local communities, SSH should introduce local events giving people in local regions a chance to be introduced to SSH. An example is the YES (Young Entrepreneurs Summit) Sydney, an event run in Camperdown that introduces people to the entrepreneurship world. SSH should take inspiration from this and create their own local events around Sydney. Another thing SSH can introduce is inviting high schools and universities to bring students into the SSH and be introduced to the space. By doing this, SSH is spreading its awareness to the next generation of entrepreneurs who may one day be looking to begin their own business.

Another lever that local communities could use to help intervene with the Sydney Startup Hub is creating a greater range of connections on a regional and international scale. Originally based within the CBD, the SSH was home to many startups all around Sydney, which would deny startups the opportunity to expand to other regions in Greater Sydney. By adapting connections throughout other regions of Sydney, the influence of local communities will help create awareness of developing new startups. Local communities influence has helped the government introduce a new startup hub in Western Sydney.

Minister of Jobs and Investment, Stuart Ayres, envisioned more opportunities for individuals to grow their startup businesses and innovation throughout Western Sydney (Brookes, 2001). Local communities have continued to use their innovative ideas by helping create a further 1,000 jobs for individuals located in Western Sydney.

Although local communities have positively impacted the SSH on a regional level, the SSH needs to use local communities of other countries to gain an understanding of how startups are evolving internationally. By connecting with the international hubs, the SSH can gain insights from international communities that have surged into creating a larger innovating world. One international hub that SSH should look to communicate with is Silicon Valley. Silicon Valley is renowned for starting the startup hub trend. The innovation hub also helped connect with other countries such as Israel, England and Sweden, that have established startup hubs that have become successful (Uzzaman, 2021). Although, the SSH have been successful with over 2,500 jobs generated, the entrepreneurial ecosystem can continue to grow with international influence.

2.3 Incentives (Why)

We believe that by exposing local communities to an environment that promotes the startup space and atmosphere, this will inherently provide a greater expansion and development of the entrepreneurial system within SSH and the City of Sydney. By creating greater exposure of SSH, this will provide exposure to different modes of channel that attracts local communities to be more inclined to seek assistance with start-ups within the community. Not only do they expand the entrepreneurial ecosystem within SSH but also provide greater job opportunities for individuals globally, seeking various different talents to assist the startup expand and succeed. With an innovative economic development, this will induce new ideas from entrepreneurs within the local community and hence will require the exposure to an environment that will allow for the entrepreneurial system within SSH to flourish and expand. Running programs and initiatives that promote SSH within the local community will create such exposure that will allow for activists to help grow the entrepreneurial system and expand it through assisting new start-ups to grow as it is in their best interests. Provided this can also provide activators with extra resources to help grow their other stakeholders and start-ups hence creating an entrepreneurial ecosystem that assists each startup to grow and overtime expand with the resources network that is provided by local communities.

Regarding our second proposal, we believe that hosting events similar to the YES summit and engaging with entrepreneurs at a younger age (Year 11 and 12) will enable Sydney Startup Hub to tap into a large pool of potential innovators to support. Additionally, visiting schools and universities will increase exposure of the SSH as evidently the large majority of UTS students in the Navigating Through Entrepreneurial Ecosystems class were completely unaware of the amazing opportunities that SSH has to offer because they never knew it existed. Being able to foster the ideas of young adults such as soon to be school graduates and those just entering university should be at the forefront of SSH's goals. By adopting our proposal of putting together an outreach team and establishing large events for school students, university students and individuals who want to learn more about entrepreneurship and how SSH can provide a whole range of assistance, SSH can aid in the growth of the Sydney startup ecosystem.

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